
Flexible Maternity Garment Using Design Details and Closures

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Abstract

The proposed research of Flexible Maternity Garment using Design Details and Closures is a study of maternity garments that are flexible to be worn by pregnant mothers. The objective of the research is to provide pregnant women with clothing that is valued, as it can be worn from pre until post-natal. Therefore, the flexibility of the garment is the innovation of the proposed product, in which the garment can expand and shrink using different design details and closures. The method of the research is through clinical and fashion data collections as well as distributed survey to respondents whom have experienced pregnancy. These data collected were categorized into three criteria (the design details, closures/fastenings and characteristics) that should be applied and avoid on maternity garments. The results of the analysis were used as guidelines in developing the proposed product. The process of developing each garment includes idea development, toiling, pre-test and prototype. As an end product, the researcher created different flexi maternity garments with differing fastening and design details.

Keywords: maternity wear, closures, fastenings, flexible

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1. Introduction

This research proposed a project product of maternity wear. From what the researcher had identified, the fashion of maternity wear collection are developing in the local market, however, not all garments are practical and meets the preferences of the mothers. In order to fulfill this issue, the researcher proposed a study of Flexible Maternity Wear through Design Details and Fastenings.

1.1. Problem Statement

The maternity wear collections that the researcher intends to propose fulfill the problems that had been identified in the fashion market in Malaysia and among the expected mothers regarding maternity garments. Through the pilot observation at local boutiques and pilot snow-ball surveys, the following problem had been identified by the researcher regarding maternity wear in the local market.

1.1.1. Lack of maternity wear collection in local boutique

There are minimal local boutiques that retail maternity wear. Mothers sometimes have trouble in looking for maternity garments. According to an article by Feride Hikmet Atak, an actress had once stated that she had hard time in finding suitable maternity garment during her pregnancy. (Feride, 2011)

1.1.2. Higher demand of maternity wear due to women's involvement in professional practice

As Malaysia striving in developing the country, with increased access to education, employment opportunities and changes in the socio-cultural environment, Malaysian women have progressed and participated effectively in all aspects of development of the country. As a result of women occupying all sectors of employment, a higher demand of maternity wear collection in fashion market has occurred. (Sally, 2011)

1.1.3. Lack of Flexible Maternity Garment

Through pilot observation and unstructured interviews to local boutiques and expected mothers, the majority of maternity wear in the market were designed for the mother to be worn during her second to third trimester only. Therefore, mothers would not buy maternity garments in large quantities, since they would only wear them during pregnancy.

1.1.4. Limited Design detail that can be adjustable in maternity garment

Through pilot observation, there are lack of adjustable closures and design detail in maternity garment. The most common adjustable medium used in maternity wear are adjustable buttons at the waist band in pants and string/band tying at the back waist and elasticated bump band in the pants. Other design details such as pin tucks and pleats were also common, however the expansion and shrinking effect is minimal.

1.2. Project Significance

The development of this project is to create an evergreen collection that can be worn at the beginning of the pre-natal, first trimester until the post-natal (after pregnancy). Mothers will be able to purchase maternity garments that can be worn at longer period. Furthermore, this will reduce the financial burden of the mothers by purchasing fewer clothes and indirectly will support the prevention of cloth pollution in Malaysia.

Moreover, the garments of this collection will be long lasting style. Therefore, the expected mothers will no longer need to purchase garment that can be worn for only few months. This project will also benefit the local fashion market, since the design will be based on the preferences of the local desires.

2. Experimental

The researcher used both quantitative and qualitative methods to obtain information to develop the proposed project. Quantitative method was in a form of questionnaire distribution whereas for qualitative, the researcher made an in depth study and evaluation based on observation and unstructured interviews. The data is used in both theoretical and practical framework.

Diagram 1. The flowchart or process of the research

2.1. Research Strategies Design Method

In this section, the researcher focuses on designing method to obtain the variables for research questions that had been outlined. The methods designed were based on the suitability of each research questions.

As for the research questions related to the suitability of garments to be worn during and after pregnancy, the method used is in a form of contextual method, whereby the research gathers information through secondary data. Clinical and fashion information was obtained through books and web. The researcher did visual observation for a better understanding in maternity changes.

On the other hand, for research questions in line with only fashion, the method designs were in a form of primary and secondary data. In order to obtain a quantitative result, the researcher had distributed surveys among 50 respondents, to identify the preferences of the mothers, the demand of the market and the problems in maternity wear. Data were also obtained through visual observation, journals and articles related to fashion trend, market and maternity wear.

2.2. Accumulating Data (findings)

In this section, the data gathers were accumulated and will be used to develop the proposed project. The data were based on the survey distributed to 50 respondents as sample for this research that was among mothers who are currently or have been pregnant. The distribution was made in Klang valley and bureau area to all races since the aim of the product was design for local market.

2.2.1. Accumulating data from literature review

Referring to literature review, the researcher had identified certain guidelines to be applied in project development. The fabrics, colours, design details and closures required in maternity garments were the highlight among the data that the researcher obtained. The characteristics that the researcher will take note in developing the garment is the usage of cotton or cotton blend as the fabric for the garment making since cotton is a fully breathable fabric, which it is cooler when worn in hot conditions. (Smeader, 2010). Furthermore, the researcher aims in applying warm and cool colour such as reddish maroon and bluish, greyish due to the positive impact of the colour on the person wearing the garment.

Suitable closures and design details were used in exploring the flexibility of the garments. Closures such as zip and buttons, design details such as flares and pleats will be used as medium for shrinking and expanding effect in development process. These details were collected from *The Fashion Designer's Directory of Shape and Style* as well as *Pattern Making for Fashion Design* (4th edition). (Travers-Spencer & Zaman, 2008) (Joseph-Armstrong, 2006)

According to a thesis study by Marilyn C. Handley (2006), the researcher stated two different changes that occurred during pregnancy. They are physical and emotional changes. The most obvious physical changes people are aware is the growth of abdomen. However, the early changes also include amenorrhea, breast enlargement and tenderness, nausea and vomiting, urinary frequency and fatigue. (Handley,2006). As pregnancies progresses, the changes that most mothers are concerned of are the changes in complexion, body size and shape, changes in gait, and loss of attractiveness. These

changes are generally addressed during prenatal care and are described as minor and are limited in duration. The symptoms generally resolve without major consequences. (Handley, 2006).

2.2.1. Accumulating data from literature review

After completing the data collection and survey, the researcher had made an in depth study evaluation based on pilot observation and unstructured interviews. The pilot observation was to visits to local maternity boutiques and other fashion areas in Putrajaya and Klang valley, in order to be updated with the local fashion trend, maternity wear style and flexible fastening used in garments. The unstructured interviews were done among women who have experienced pregnancy. The content of the interview were regarding the physical and emotional changes during pregnancy, problems that they faced during pregnancy and existed maternity garment in market.

Furthermore, based on the analysis from data collected in chapter 4, the researcher had listed the criteria and closures that should be applied and avoid in designing the proposed product. The criteria are the design details, closures and the preferred characteristic on maternity wear.

2.3. Method of Developing the Proposed Product through Fashion Practice

In this section, the researcher will develop the design based on the criteria that had been listed from the data collected from literature review and the result of data analysis

Applying The Analysis Data Into Design (Proposed Project) & Project Development

Diagram 2. Process of Fashion Practice

The early idea development was through sketches and draping. In the sketching process, the researcher had used computer software (adobe illustrator and photoshop) to place the lines and shapes on croquis (figure). The sketches were then refined using collage and mix media. The 2D sketches were transformed into toile, which is a mockup of the garment, to test the pattern and ensure that the garment fits properly before it is cut out onto the real fabric and constructed. The adjustments of the garments were done in this process. The further step was to produce four garments. The garment was then evaluated based on the mother's opinion and views

3. Results and Discussion

In this section the researcher had experiment and explores different design and materials to produce the proposed product. In this chapter, the researcher had arranged the process into design selection (idea development), transforming the 2D image into 3D prototype, refining the product to meet the proposed criteria and pre-evaluation.

These data were obtained through distribution of questionnaires. The results from the respondents were than analyzed in SPSS in order to calculate the percentage of the respondents' problem and requirement. Based on the results of the survey, the researcher had identified the characteristics, closures and design detail that should be applied in developing the product.

3.1. Analyzed data for Design Development

The researcher had listed the criteria that should be applied and avoid in designing the proposed product based on the result of the survey. These criteria are the design details, closures and the preferred characteristics on maternity wear.

CRITERIA	APPLIED	AVOID
Design Detail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pintuck - Flares - Pleats - Hidden Pocket 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Belt - Sashes
Closures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zip - Buttons - Snap buttons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hook & eye
Characteristics of Garments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible - Expand and shrink (must occur at bust & abdomen) - Comfort - Suitable fabric - Long Lasting 	
Criteria to meet the Physical changes of mothers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expansion and shrink effect on the abdomen and chest - The fastenings should be practical, such as neckline opening, centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complicated placements of fastenings such as zip/ button at the back

	front opening	
Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Breathable fabrics, e.g cotton - Medium weight fabric - Easily care - Minimal Motifs/ pattern must be placed suitable to mothers body silhouette 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avoid heavy weight materials as tops garments, such as denim

Table 1. List of Criteria based on the Data Analysis

3.2. Design Selection / Process

In this section, the designer focused on developing ideas through different techniques.

3.2.1. Developing Basic Design

In this process, the researcher had done some sketches in using different media such as mix media, collage and computer software (Adobe Illustrator and Photoshop). The idea was to obtain form and silhouette of maternity garment and the flexibility of the garment (expand and shrinking effect)

The researcher had chosen the basic elements and principles of art and designs as the subject matter. The design was then refine based on the criteria that had been outlined from the analyzed data (as shown in Table 1).

3.2.2. Placement of Motifs into Design

The researcher had also explored placement of lines motifs to obtain silhouette and form. The researcher had explored different techniques using sketches and computer to obtained different silhouette and illusion. The medium and technique used in this process were mix media, collage and Adobe Photoshop.

Figure 3.1. Placement of Lines to obtain silhouette and form

The subsequent step of Idea exploration is the researcher refines the design to meet the criteria and aims of the research. The designer used the process of add and remove to refine the design. The design must be functional and have aesthetic value. The criteria were of the followings:

- Functional : Flexible: expanding and shrinking effect (chest & abdomen)
- Aesthetic : Minimal design motifs
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Figure 3.2. Refining the silhouette to meet the criteria (Design 1)

Figure 3.3. Refining the silhouette to meet the criteria (Design 2)

Figure 3.4. Refining the silhouette to meet the criteria

3.3. Transforming the image of 2D to 3D

In this section, the researcher used the sketches image during the idea development process to a 3D prototype. This will give a total look of the garment so that the researcher can identify the problems at the early stage from different views. The techniques used by the researcher is draping on dummy and producing toile.

Figure 3.5. Transforming the 2D Images sketches to 3D prototype samples (Design 1)

In this proposed prototype, exploration was on the flexibility effect at the underarm. The suggested adjustable closure used is buttons and loops. After completing the toile, the researcher identifies that the garment does not fully expand. The expansion and shrinking effect only occur at the bust. Based on the criteria, the adjustment of expansion must occur at the bust and abdomen, since that is the main physical changes occur during pregnancy. As a result, a hidden pleat using invisible zip as adjustable closures is suggested at the centre front for a wider expansion effect for this proposed product.

Figure 3.6. Transforming the 2D Images sketches to 3D prototype samples (Design 2)

In this proposed prototype, exploration was on the flexibility effect at the princess line. After completing the toile, the researcher refines the idea by placing a hidden pleats with invisible zip were only placed at the back and front princess line, however at the pleats were also inserted at the centre front as well as centre back for a wider garment expansion. The opening of the zip must be adjustable until the bust. In addition, a placement of pocket was added to this design to enhance the functionality.

Figure 3.7. Transforming the 2D Images sketches to 3D prototype samples (Design 3)

In the final ideation development, researcher designs a multi-function garment which can be worn as a top and skirt. In the early stage of this garment making, the researcher uses bias cut flare as the flexibility medium. However, the expansion was not wide enough to be worn during pregnancy. As a result, additional hidden pleats with invisible zip is placed at the back and front princess line.

3.4. Refining the Product

The researcher has decided that the proposed product (maternity garment) must have aesthetic value and functionality. The researcher refines the product based on the findings of the survey. (Refer to Table 1). The components that researchers focus on were the closures and design details, pattern and garment construction and the material used to obtain a flexible maternity wear.

3.4.1 Closures and Design Details

Based on the result of the analyzed data, the closures that the mothers prefer during pregnancy are buttons, zip, hook and bar, strap buttons and velcro. As for the design detail on the garments, most mothers prefer to have garment with flares, pin tucks and hidden pocket. Therefore the researcher aims in designing maternity garments with these closures and design details.

3.4.2 Pattern and Garment Construction

The technical pattern of the prototype was made using pattern block construction and draping. The working patterns were transferred to final patterns to produce the actual and final prototype.

3.4.3 Fabrics and Materials

The most suitable fabrics and materials for local maternity wear are light to medium weight fabrics. The best and common fabric suggested by the clinical is cotton fabric. Referring to the data collected, the characteristics of cotton fabric is moisture control, hypoallergenic, insulation, waterproof, comfort and durability. The reason to this is that 100% cotton is a fully breathable fabric, which it is cooler when worn in hot conditions. (Smeader,2010). Furthermore, an article by Peterman (2009) had stated that the advantages of cotton clothing are breathable and has ability to control the body moisture.

Therefore researcher had chosen to apply cotton as material in maternity garment and other textile as a substitute to this proposed design. The colours chosen for this design were warm and cool colour with minimal motifs, since more than 50% of the respondents prefer minimal motifs.(Table 1)

3.5. Technical Drawing of Complete Design

Figure 3.8 shows a technical drawing of design 1. The shrinking and expansion medium are buttons and loop at the armhole, loop and band at the side waist and invisible zip with pleats at the centre front.

Figure 3.8. Technical Drawing of Design 1

Figure 3.9. Technical Drawing of Design 2

Figure 3.9 shows a technical drawing of design 2. The shrinking and expansion medium are buttons and loop at the side waist and invisible zip with pleats at the centre front, front princess line, centre back and back princess line. A placement of pockets at the side is additional function to the design.

Figure 3.11. Technical Drawing of Design 3

Figure 3.11 shows a technical drawing of design 3. The researcher applied a multi-functional garment, which can be worn as a top and a skirt. The medium flexibility of this design is the adjustable pleats at the front and back princess line with invisible zip, as well as the flare of the garment. An invisible zip is placed at side seam, for armhole when worn as a top.

4. Discussion

In the process of development, three design products were made to meet the objectives of this research. The objectives were the following:-

- Provide pregnant women with clothing that is valued as it can be worn during pre to post-natal.

Design 1 until 3 were designed with adjustable characteristics which means they can shrink and expand, to be worn throughout their pregnancy period, pre and post-natal period. In addition, design 3 were designed as functional garments that can be adjusted into different garments which are skirt, cape or dress, to be worn during pre and post-natal based on the suitability of the mother.

- Provide pregnant women with clothing that can be expand and shrink using fastenings and design details.

Since the body of the mother grew gradually from month to month, the researcher designed garments with fastenings and design details as the medium of expansion and shrinking effect of the garments. The adjustments were designed for the adjustment of bust and waist, since those are the main body changes during pregnancy. Design details of flared and pleated which created wider expansion were chosen rather than pin tuck. Whereas the closures, zips and draw stings were used to control the expansion and shrinking sizes, rather than hook and bar, or snap buttons, since its adjustment is limited.

In the process of developing and exploring the proposed product, the researcher had developed more critical analysis of what each garment should include and its function. The researcher had started with the idea that flexibility of the garment is from big into small or small to big, but with further development gives the idea of developing the garment into useful garments for pre or post pregnancy. In the first design, the researcher explored different closures but is only minimally explored onto the garment for the purpose of practicality and comfort of the pregnant mother. However, the researcher explores different types of closures, design panels and functional design details, such as the pocket to the second design. The development was not only focusing in the expansion of bust and abdomen but around the body. This development eventually gives an innovative look to this design.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion the researcher has achieved the aims and objectives of the research, in providing pregnant women with flexible clothing that can be worn from pre until post-natal period by adjusting different closures and design details. Through exploration of different closures as a medium in developing the expansion and shrinking of the garment, the researcher had exposed other innovative functions of closures rather than only using them to fasten the garment. Furthermore, this research will also provide ideas of how a functional garment can also be a wearable stylish garment rather than as an art to wear.

5.1 Recommendation

In completing the research studies, the researcher offers a few recommendations for future related research. The main development of the product was aimed in creating innovation on the silhouette of the garment and only minimal studies were made on the fabric. Therefore, it is recommended that a further study on suitable technical textile such as anti-radiation fabric as a continuation of this research.

Moreover, the colours of the proposed product were derived from the psychological colour studies. However, an evaluation of colour mood has not yet been done, due to the limitation of expertise and time. Therefore, a further study to evaluate the mother's colour mood when wearing the garments is suggested

In addition, the researcher would also suggest a nursing maternity garment for a future study as a continuation of this research, since this research proposed a flexible garment that can be worn during the post-natal period.

A suggestion of exploration on the functions of the closures other than fastening the garment would also be a good attempt for a future study. In this research, the researcher explored closures as medium of expanding and shrinking the garment. However, the researcher believed that closures can also be used as functional decorative accessories such as zip into a belt or buttons as buckle or brooches.

Furthermore, the researcher suggests local designers could apply the idea of shrinking and expanding using design details and fastenings on garments that can be marketed such as women's uniform or uniform body troops (e.g. police, hospital uniform, etc.). This will create awareness of functional garments to fashion consumers, rather than acts as an art expression (art to wear)

6. Patents

The technical drawings of design and research of the maternity wear collection has intellectual property with reference number AR2019003137.

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